

Retarding Influence of Phosphates and Wheat-straw on Nitrogen Loss in Soils Treated with Ammonium Sulphate and Ammonium Nitrate

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It has been observed that phosphates retard the nitrogen loss forming stable compounds like ammonium phosphate. Wheat-straw helped in checking the nitrogen loss and increasing the available N and P_2O_5 contents. pH of the samples was also found to be affected by phosphate, nitrogen and carbon interactions. This finding was substantiated by laboratory and pot experiments conducted with alluvial soils of Varanasi (U.P.).

SUPPLY of readily available nitrogen is generally met by the application of nitrogenous fertilizers. Inorganic nitrogen compounds like ammonium and nitrates usually suffer several types of losses from the soil viz., loss of nitrogen in the gaseous form, loss through immobilization, loss due to leaching etc. On account of such losses the recovery of nitrogen, when applied as fertilizer or manure, by crops is not high. Both the organic and inorganic fractions of the soil have the ability to react with the available forms of nitrogen in such a way as to make it unavailable to higher plants.

Sohn and Peach¹ have carefully studied the retention and fixation of ammonium applied as salts of strong acids to different soils. Allison *et al*² have shown that the presence of organic matter hinders the fixation of ammonia by blocking the entrance of ammonium ions between the clay plates. Dhar³ has also suggested the loss of nitrogen during ammonification and nitrification processes due to the formation of a very unstable substance, ammonium nitrite, which decomposes very easily producing nitrogen gas.

An attempt has been made in this paper to investigate the influence of phosphates and wheat-straw on retardation of nitrogen loss in soils treated with ammonium sulphate and ammonium nitrate.

Experimental

200 g sandy loam soil from Varanasi (U.P.) passing through 50 mesh sieve was taken in dishes. Required amounts of superphosphate, Trichinopoly rockphosphate, Tata basic slag and bone meal at the rate of 0.25% P_2O_5 and $(NH_4)_2SO_4$ and NH_4NO_3 at the rate of 0.1% N were incorporated in the dishes and thoroughly mixed with wheat-straw application at the rate of 0.5% carbon level.

Moisture was maintained at 20% level throughout the experimental period. At regular intervals of 60, 120 and 180 days, composite soil samples were taken out from each set and were analysed for total carbon, available N, available P_2O_5 and pH.

Methods of estimations employed are as mentioned by Jackson⁴.

TABLE 1—ANALYSES OF SOIL AND FERTILIZER MATERIALS

	Estimation	Content	Estimation
Soil	pH	7.8	Wheat straw
	Total N	0.057%	Total C = 36.6%
	Total P_2O_5	0.138%	Total N = 0.616%
	Total CaO	0.894%	Superphosphate
	Total MgO	0.437%	Total P = 16.2%
	Total K_2O	0.994%	Rockphosphate
	Total C	0.601%	Total P = 23.6%
	Available N	40.0 ppm	Tata basic slag
	Available P_2O_5	4.6 ppm	Total P = 7.53%
	Sand	56.3%	Bone meal
	Silt	30.2%	Total P = 21.7%
	Clay	6.5%	Total N = 4.4%

Results and Discussion

The experimental results recorded in Tables 2 to 4 show that in all sets there is a marked loss of nitrogen after 60, 120 and 180 days. Nitrogen loss in ammonium sulphate sets has been observed to be higher as compared to ammonium nitrate ones. Phosphatic sources viz. rockphosphate, Tata basic slag and bone meal have been found to have significant influence over retention of nitrogen. Superphosphate being acidic in reaction does not seem to check the nitrogen loss. Application of phosphates along with 0.5% carbon introduction in the form of wheat-straw also help in checking the nitrogen loss. Available nitrogen content of the soil samples is also found to be influenced by the application of phosphates. Carbon introduction accelerated the availability of the nitrogen in all the sets which is revealed by data in Tables 2 to 4. pH values of the soil samples has also been found to be affected by the application of nitrogenous fertilizers, phosphates and wheat-straw. Effect of N and P fertilizers on soil pH variation has been reported by Volk and Tidmore⁵, Grunes⁶ and others.

TABLE 2—ANALYSES OF SOIL AFTER 60 DAYS WITH AMMONIUM SULPHATE AND AMMONIUM NITRATE AMENDMENTS

Treatment	Total C %	% N loss	Av. P ₂ O ₅ ppm	Av. N ppm	pH
With ammonium sulphate					
1. Control	0.057	32.0	4.6	51.0	7.6
2. S.P.	0.055	36.5	5.8	50.0	7.4
3. S.P. + W.S.	0.061	30.0	5.9	50.5	7.3
4. R.P.	0.059	28.0	4.9	54.0	7.6
5. R.P. + W.S.	0.064	24.5	5.0	52.0	7.2
6. T.B.S.	0.052	25.0	4.8	51.5	7.6
7. T.B.S. + W.S.	0.062	22.0	5.1	50.0	7.1
8. B.M.	0.055	20.5	5.0	55.0	7.5
9. B.M. + W.S.	0.064	16.5	5.2	57.5	7.3
With ammonium nitrate					
1. Control	0.059	28.0	4.8	53.5	7.8
2. S.P.	0.055	31.5	5.8	50.5	7.3
3. S.P. + W.S.	0.063	26.0	6.0	54.5	7.3
4. R.P.	0.060	25.0	4.9	58.5	7.6
5. R.P. + W.S.	0.068	20.0	5.8	65.0	7.2
6. T.B.S.	0.061	23.5	5.0	57.0	7.6
7. T.B.S. + W.S.	0.068	20.0	5.8	65.0	7.2
8. B.M.	0.060	21.0	6.0	56.0	7.4
9. B.M. + W.S.	0.066	18.5	6.7	63.5	7.2

S.P. superphosphate
W.S. wheat-straw
R.P. rockphosphate
T.B.S. Tata basic slag
B.M. bone meal

TABLE 3—ANALYSES OF SOIL AFTER 120 DAYS WITH AMMONIUM SULPHATE AND AMMONIUM NITRATE AMENDMENTS

Treatment	Total C %	% N loss	Av. P ₂ O ₅ ppm	Av. N ppm	pH
With ammonium sulphate					
1. Control	0.054	40.0	5.0	47.0	7.6
2. S.P.	0.051	47.0	6.2	45.5	7.4
3. S.P. + W.S.	0.060	39.0	6.5	48.5	7.4
4. R.P.	0.056	36.0	6.0	50.0	7.5
5. R.P. + W.S.	0.062	31.5	6.7	51.5	7.4
6. T.B.S.	0.055	34.5	6.2	55.5	7.5
7. T.B.S. + W.S.	0.060	26.0	6.7	57.0	7.5
8. B.M.	0.050	28.5	6.3	53.0	7.3
9. B.M. + W.S.	0.061	21.0	6.9	58.5	7.1
With ammonium nitrate					
1. Control	0.054	35.5	5.3	49.5	7.8
2. S.P.	0.050	37.0	6.4	47.0	7.3
3. S.P. + W.S.	0.061	34.5	6.7	51.5	7.1
4. R.P.	0.054	30.0	6.5	55.0	7.5
5. R.P. + W.S.	0.059	27.5	6.9	57.5	7.4
6. T.B.S.	0.056	27.0	6.4	53.0	7.4
7. T.B.S. + W.S.	0.061	25.0	6.9	61.5	7.2
8. B.M.	0.053	25.0	6.5	54.5	7.2
9. B.M. + W.S.	0.061	23.5	7.2	61.5	7.2

TABLE 4—ANALYSES OF SOIL AFTER 180 DAYS WITH AMMONIUM SULPHATE AND AMMONIUM NITRATE AMENDMENTS.

Treatment	Total C %	% N loss	Av. P ₂ O ₅ ppm	Av. N ppm	pH
With ammonium sulphate					
1. Control	0.049	46.0	5.2	48.2	7.6
2. S.P.	0.047	48.5	6.7	47.0	7.4
3. S.P. + W.S.	0.057	40.0	7.3	50.0	7.3
4. R.P.	0.051	37.5	6.3	52.2	7.5
5. R.P. + W.S.	0.060	33.0	6.9	54.5	7.4
6. T.B.S.	0.052	37.0	6.3	56.0	7.5
7. T.B.S. + W.S.	0.060	29.0	6.9	59.0	7.4
8. B.M.	0.049	32.5	6.5	57.5	7.2
9. B.M. + W.S.	0.058	24.0	7.4	60.5	7.2
With ammonium nitrate					
1. Control	0.050	40.0	5.0	44.0	7.5
2. S.P.	0.049	42.5	6.6	46.6	7.4
3. S.P. + W.S.	0.062	38.5	7.5	47.5	7.3
4. R.P.	0.051	35.0	6.4	58.0	7.5
5. R.P. + W.S.	0.057	30.0	6.9	62.5	7.4
6. T.B.S.	0.049	35.5	6.5	55.5	7.5
7. T.B.S. + W.S.	0.058	29.0	7.0	64.0	7.4
8. B.M.	0.049	30.0	6.6	57.0	7.4
9. B.M. + W.S.	0.057	23.5	7.6	67.0	7.3

TABLE 5—INFLUENCE OF PHOSPHATIC SOURCES AND WHEAT-STRAW ON N AND P UPTAKE BY WHEAT WITH AMMONIUM SULPHATE AND AMMONIUM NITRATE INCORPORATION

Treatment	Dry wt. g/pot	N uptake %	P uptake %	N/P ratio	Crude protein %
With ammonium sulphate					
1. Control	10.8	1.08	0.365	2.95	6.75
2. S.P.	16.5	1.32	0.390	3.38	8.25
3. S.P. + W.S.	18.0	1.48	0.425	3.48	9.25
4. R.P.	15.2	1.28	0.382	3.35	8.00
5. R.P. + W.S.	16.5	1.41	0.392	3.59	8.80
6. T.B.S.	15.8	1.21	0.386	3.13	7.56
7. T.B.S. + W.S.	17.8	1.29	0.392	3.29	8.06
8. B.M.	15.5	1.30	0.388	3.35	8.12
9. B.M. + W.S.	17.4	1.45	0.415	3.49	9.06
C.D. (5%)	1.69	0.26	0.041	0.29	1.64
With ammonium nitrate					
1. Control	10.5	1.08	0.366	2.95	6.75
2. S.P.	16.0	1.30	0.386	3.36	8.12
3. S.P. + W.S.	16.8	1.45	0.420	3.45	9.06
4. R.P.	18.3	1.25	0.385	3.24	7.81
5. R.P. + W.S.	15.0	1.40	0.395	3.54	8.75
6. T.B.S.	16.3	1.27	0.388	3.27	7.93
7. T.B.S. + W.S.	18.0	1.32	0.395	3.34	8.25
8. B.M.	15.5	1.30	0.390	3.33	8.12
9. B.M. + W.S.	17.9	1.40	0.410	3.41	8.75
C.D. (5%)	1.54	0.19	0.017	0.54	1.27

Role of phosphates in stabilising the available nitrogen and retarding the nitrogen loss in different sets may be due to production of ammonium phosphate which is more stable than nitrate and ammonical compounds. Carbon incorporation in the form of wheat-straw can also be significantly correlated with the increase in the available P₂O₅ and nitrogen contents of soil and also influence the C/N ratio and pH of the soil. pH may influence the solubility of the phosphates which help the release of more available P₂O₅ for the plants.

Increase in the availability of phosphates by adding carbonaceous matter may be due to the

production of carbonic acid and other organic acids by decomposition of wheat-straw. Estimation of total carbon of the soil samples was also conducted in all the sets and it has been observed that the oxidation of carbon is higher in treatments where wheat-straw and phosphate have been incorporated.

A pot experiment has been conducted with the same soil sample by growing wheat variety RR₂₁ as test crop. It is observed that uptake of nitrogen is higher in treatments receiving phosphates and wheat-straw which show similar trend of results as obtained in the laboratory experiment. Increased

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available P_2O_5 content of soil caused by the addition of phosphates and organic material incorporation might have resulted in the higher dry matter production as recorded in Table 5. Caldwell⁷ also found increased crop uptake from P^{32} labelled monocalcium phosphate when intimately mixed with ammonium sulphate, ammonium nitrate or ammonium chloride but not in separate application. The most likely chemical explanation of the beneficial effects of nitrogenous salts is an increase of the solubility of the phosphates or their reaction products.

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